

VOCABULARY PREPARATION IN TEACHING LISTENING TO MULTI-LEVEL LEARNERS.

Madoripova Dilzoda

student, Uzbek state world languages university

Allakulova Sevara

student, Uzbek state world languages university

Annotation

The learning of vocabulary is important part in foreign language learning. The meanings of new words are very frequently emphasized, whether in books or in verbal communication. Vocabulary is considered as the central in language teaching and is of paramount importance to a language learner. Vocabulary is a basic of one learns a foreign language. Few research indicate that teaching vocabulary can be considered as problematic, as some teachers are not really sure about the best practice in the teaching and sometimes not really aware how to start forming an instructional emphasis on the vocabulary learning Through this article, the writer summarizes the related research that focus on the importance of vocabulary and explaining many techniques used by some English teachers and lecturer when teaching English, as well as writer’s personal view of the issues.

Key words: multilevel learners, insufficient vocabulary, script, cognitive process, productive usage

Аннотация

Изучение словарного запаса является важной частью изучения иностранного языка. Значения новых слов очень часто подчеркиваются как в книгах, так и в устном общении. Словарный запас считается центральным элементом преподавания языка и имеет первостепенное значение для изучающего язык. Словарный запас является основой изучения иностранного языка. Немногие исследования показывают, что преподавание словарного запаса можно считать проблематичным, поскольку некоторые учителя не совсем уверены в наилучшей практике преподавания и иногда не совсем понимают, как начать формировать учебный акцент на изучении словарного запаса. В этой статье автор резюмирует соответствующие исследования, которые фокусируются на важности словарного запаса и объясняют многие методы, используемые некоторыми учителями английского языка и лекторами при преподавании английского языка, а также личный взгляд писателей на проблемы.

Ключевые слова: многоуровневые обучающиеся, недостаточный словарный запас, сценарий, когнитивный процесс, продуктивное использование.

Annotatsiya

Chet tilini o'rganishda so'z boyligini o'rganish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Yangi so'zlarning ma'nolari kitoblarda yoki og'zaki muloqotda juda tez-tez ta'kidlanadi. Lug'at

til o'rgatishda markaziy o'rinni egallaydi va til o'rganuvchi uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. Chet tilini o'rganish uchun lug'at asosiy hisoblanadi. Bir nechta tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, lug'atni o'rgatish muammoli deb hisoblanishi mumkin, chunki ba'zi o'qituvchilar o'qitishdagi eng yaxshi amaliyotga ishonchlari komil emaslar va ba'zida lug'atni o'rganishga o'rgatuvchi urg'uni qanday shakllantirishni bilishmaydi. lug'atning ahamiyati va ingliz tilini o'rgatishda ba'zi ingliz o'qituvchilari va o'qituvchilari tomonidan qo'llaniladigan ko'plab usullarni tushuntirishga, shuningdek, yozuvchining muammolarga shaxsiy nuqtai nazariga qaratilgan tegishli tadqiqotlar.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'p bosqichli o'quvchilar, lug'atning etarli emasligi, skript, kognitiv jarayon, samarali foydalanish

Introduction

Topical preparation is particularly important when the texts may introduce culturally unfamiliar concepts. Background knowledge is represented in human memory through scripts, that is, sets of expectations people have about general concepts, places, situations, actions and their sequences. Scripts play an important role in human information processing and they tend to be culture-bound (Buck, 2001). Therefore, the extent to which the listener may share background knowledge with the speakers is an important issue to consider at the preparation stage.

One simple way to introduce the topic is to give students some topical questions for discussion. For example, if listening is going to be about food, asking students to discuss questions such as *What kind of food do you like? How healthy are your eating habits? Do you prefer to eat out or at home? What is the most unusual food you have tried?* And so on can be a good warm-up activity. Insufficient vocabulary knowledge is a frequent cause of listening comprehension problems. Due to limited vocabulary size and problems with the perception of acoustic forms, learners often experience difficulties in processing audio input. Learners may not know the words that appear in the spoken discourse, or they may not be able to recognize them in the strings of connected speech. Failure to understand the input correctly also means that learners will have difficulties anticipating the upcoming discourse. Studies from L1 showed that native speakers use context to make predictions about the utterances that are likely to follow (Ur,1998) If the listener knows how the sentence is likely to finish, the closing words become redundant and he/she can focus on the next significant piece of information. As language learners often do not have enough linguistic knowledge, they cannot take advantage of contextual redundancy in the way that native speakers can. More mental effort is needed to process information which means that less information can be stored at one time in the short-term memory.

Sufficient vocabulary preparation is also important because lexical knowledge entails background knowledge. The more a learner knows about a word, the more he/she is likely to be aware of the semantic links in the structure of a text and consequently the more likely he/she is to activate the relevant background knowledge crucial for text comprehension (Nattinger, J.R. and DeCarrico,1992). Recognition of word-forms triggers

preexisting world knowledge as well as knowledge of any associated words or concepts related to that word. For example, when the word “tuxedo,” is encountered in a text, the cognitive processes that are attempting to make sense of the text do not just access it as “a formal suit of clothing.”

Vocabulary activities at the preparations stage, therefore, have three main objectives: (a) to familiarize the learners with the meaning and the form of new words, (b) to help learners recognize lexical items in the strings of connected speech, (c) to promote productive usage of the target words necessary for the reconstruction stage (Sachs, J.S. (1967).

Collocation-based lexical instruction seems to be an effective way of achieving this goal. One activity that was found to be effective is a *Collocation Crossword*. The students are given a list of the target words with example sentences and definitions. After that, they are asked to complete a crossword where the clues are collocates that go with the target words. For each target word, two sentences are given. To facilitate retention, typical collocates should be highlighted. Here is one example from the Model Lesson:

It is a custom that someone _____ **water over** a guest’s hands.

I _____ **wine into** your glass by mistake. (*Target word: *to pour*)

This activity promotes four different aspects of word knowledge: written and spoken form, meaning, grammar and collocates. In order to fill in the gaps, the learners must recall the meaning of the target words. As some sentences require different inflectional forms, learners also have to think about grammatical properties of the words. Highlighted collocates give typical examples of the usage of the target words. In order to complete the crossword, the students have to pay attention to spelling (Willingham, 2006) Finally, an in-class check of the students’ answers gives the teacher an opportunity to correct possible pronunciation errors and draw students’ attention to how the target words may sound in the stream of fast connected speech allowing learners to acquire pronunciation, stress and intonation patterns.

Conclusion

The Vocabulary preparation combines conventional teaching procedures such as topical warm-up, explicit vocabulary instruction and possibly grammar correction with a new type of meaning-based listening activity and cooperative learning. The procedure entails both language decoding (dictation) and its encoding (reconstruction) and, as a result, enhances both students’ listening and communication skills. It pushes learners to produce a meaningful and accurate text and to reflect on their choices.

References

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